

Fabrication and Spin Tests of Composite Flywheels

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ABSTRACT

Energy storage flywheels consisted of carbon fiber epoxy composite rims and aluminum or carbon fabric cloth epoxy composite hubs were designed, fabricated and tested. The composite rims were 380mm in outer diameter and 300mm in inner diameter with a thickness of 25mm. The test rotor with a aluminum hub was spun to maximum peripheral speed of 982m/s on burst test. This corresponds to an energy density, based upon total rotor weight, of approximately 71Wh/kg. Another rotor, made use of a four rims configuration, was tested to 800m/s in success with no damage and no dynamic problem. The energy stored in the rotor is more than 500Wh and the energy density is about 55Wh/kg at that speed. The rotor with a composite hub was tested to the peripheral speed of 820m/s. It was restricted by rotor dynamic problems.

INTRODUCTION

TOKYO ELECTRIC POWER Co., Inc. and ISHIKAWAJIMA-HARIMA HEAVY INDUSTRIES Co., Ltd. have developed a program of a feasibility study on the large scale flywheel systems for peak-load leveling. The major object of the program is to demonstrate the feasibility of the energy storage flywheel systems. This program includes following tasks:

- (1) The system analysis of the electric power storage facility.
 - (2) The design, fabrication and testing of composite rotors.
- The status of the latter part of this program will be described in this paper.

Composite flywheels have been expected to be a way of storing such energies as the breaking energy of motor cars and the peak-load energy in the utility system. A few experiments on the composite flywheels have been succeeded to verify the excellent performance of them, whereas many ideas on their shapes or designs have been presented and many tests have been attempted.⁽¹⁾ The reason for this seems to be in the complexity of the shapes of the flywheel rims or their spokes.

In this study, circumferentially filament wound carbon fiber epoxy composite rims supported by plate type aluminum hubs or carbon fiber epoxy quasi-isotropic composite hubs have been tested and resulted in success. The cross section of the rims is rectangular, the simplest shape for filamentally

reinforced composites. The key to this success was the simple shapes of the plate type hubs.

FUNDAMENTAL DESIGN OF A COMPOSITE FLYWHEEL

Fibrous composites have been regarded as the excellent materials for the energy storage flywheel depending on their high specific strengths, that are the idealized highest strengths of composites. On the other hand, the stress distribution in the flywheel disk or rim is not uniaxial and the inner to outer radius ratio has to be considered. The expressions for radial stress σ_r and hoop stress σ_θ at the radius r are:(2)

$$\sigma_r = c_1 \left[c_2 \left(\frac{r}{b} \right)^{\lambda-1} + c_3 \left(\frac{r}{b} \right)^{-\lambda-1} - \left(\frac{r}{b} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$\sigma_\theta = c_1 \left[\lambda c_2 \left(\frac{r}{b} \right)^{\lambda-1} - \frac{\lambda^2 + 3\nu_{r\theta}}{3 + \nu_{r\theta}} \left(\frac{r}{b} \right)^2 - \lambda c_3 \left(\frac{r}{b} \right)^{-\lambda-1} \right]$$

where

$$c_1 = \frac{(3 + \nu_{r\theta}) \rho \omega^2 b^2}{9 - \lambda^2}, \quad c_2 = \frac{1 - \left(\frac{a}{b} \right)^{\lambda+3}}{1 - \left(\frac{a}{b} \right)^{2\lambda}}, \quad c_3 = \frac{1 - \left(\frac{a}{b} \right)^{-\lambda+3}}{1 - \left(\frac{a}{b} \right)^{-2\lambda}}$$

$$\lambda = \sqrt{(\text{hoop modulus } E_\theta) / (\text{radial modulus } E_r)}$$

The stress distributions of the circumferential stress and the radial stress of rotating carbon fiber epoxy composite rims which have the inner to outer radius ratios of 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, and 0.9 are shown in Figure 2, where it can be seen that the differences between the maximum values of the radial stresses of each inner to outer ratio are far more than those of the circumferential ones. Assuming that the circumferential allowable stress is 1000MPa and the radial one is 30MPa, the maximum rotational speed for the rim of each inner to outer radius ratio will be obtained. For a rim of small inner to outer radius ratio, the maximum radial stress reaches its allowable stress at lower rotational speed than that at which the maximum circumferential stress reaches its allowable stress, and for a rim of large inner to outer radius ratio, i.e. nearly unity, the maximum circumferential stress reaches the allowable stress at lower rotational speed than that at which the maximum radial stress reaches its allowable stress.

Then, we got the solid line of Figure 3 as maximum peripheral speed, dotted line as energy capacity and chain line as energy density (energy per unit weight). The optimum inner to outer radius ratio where both circumferential and radial maximum stress will reach their allowable stress simultaneously and the energy capacity will be the largest for a given outer radius, is about 0.75 for this case, and will be varied for other allowable stresses.

We have no data for these allowable stresses at present, but considering that the longitudinal strength of a carbon fiber epoxy unidirectional composite reinforced by high strength type carbon fiber is about 1500MPa and the transverse strength is about 50 to 80MPa, it is reasonable to regard the optimum inner to outer radius ratio to be 0.75 to 0.8. Then, it was decided that the rim of the test rotor was 380mm in outer diameter, 300mm in inner diameter (radius ratio of 0.75) and 25mm in thickness. The maximum stress in circumferential direction is 900MPa and that in radial direction is 30MPa at the rotational speed of 800m/s in calculation.

FABRICATION OF THE COMPOSITE RIMS

The flywheel rims were fabricated by filament winding method using a carbon

roving TORAYCA T300-15000 filaments and a Epikoto 828-NMA-TDMP (100:80:1 by weight) resin system cured at 90°C 2hr and 170°C 20hr. The outside surface of the cured rims were lathed to the designed outside diameter.

Since the transverse strength of filament wound composites limit the energy storage capacity of a composite rim flywheel design, many efforts must be paid to improve through investigation of the fabricating methods the transverse strength of filament wound composites. Especially in the fabrication of the circumferentially wound rims, the residual stress caused by the curing must be considered. Our another study on the residual stress in a thick composite disk showed that the residual stress of the radial direction in a thick rim whose inner to outer radius ratio was such like 0.5 was so large that the circumferential cracks along the fibers occurred with the probability of about fifty percent during the cure or, very rare case, during being left in room temperature after the cure. Then, we must take into consideration the radial residual stress, the maximum value of which for the radius ratio of 0.79 and the curing condition of this fabrication had been estimated about 5MPa.

DESIGN OF HUB

Since the circumferential Young's modulus of carbon fiber epoxy composite, the fiber volume fraction of which is about sixty percent, is 150GPa, the displacement of the inner circumference for the radial direction will become 0.67% of its radius for the maximum circumferential allowable stress of 1000MPa. The value is too large to support the rotating rim by ordinary means of high speed rotating machines. For this reason, the hub must be designed to satisfy the following strict requirements:

(1) Follow the rim's inside displacement caused by high speed rotation and support the rim stiffly.

(2) Withstand the stresses caused by high rotating speed.

Consideration have been given to two types of hub designs. The hub designs on aluminum plate type and composite plate type are described below.

Aluminum Hub

Figure 4 illustrates the flywheel rotor with a composite rim and a aluminum hub. The basic configuration of the aluminum hub is a tapered thickness disk having slits around it to avoid the circumferential stress. In order to increase the outside displacement without the radial stress increase, the centerline of the thickness curves like the schema shown in Figure 5. The actual inclination of the line, however, is so small that it cannot be noticed at a glance. The detail shape was decided by the stress analysis using FEM. Owing to these designs, the aluminum hubs made of 7075-T6 aluminum alloy had been confirmed to satisfy the above requirements until the rotational speed of more than 800m/s.

Four aluminum hubs were made. Two of them were used for single rim rotors and the others were used for the multi-rim rotor.

Composite Hub

The second model of hub is discussed on carbon fiber epoxy composite inplane quasi-isotropic plate type hub. The basic concept of the hub shape is as same as that of former aluminum hub, namely, the mid plane of the disk is curved, but there is no slits around it.

The quasi-isotropic hub is consisted of TORAYCA fabric carbon cloth #6341 and the epoxy resin system which is the same as that used in rims. They were built of 12 layers of the fabric carbon cloth with each layer oriented so that the axis of the fabric was 60 degrees from the fibers in the preceding layers. This 60 degrees progressive lay-up was arranged so that the hub would have mid-plane symmetry. The fabric cloth layers were set into a steel mold and the resin was impregnated by vacuum injection. The fiber volume fraction was estimated to be about 60% by letting the thickness 4.6mm.

SPIN TESTS

For the spin tests, a test facility having a 4-inch diameter air turbine whose rotational speed capability of 60,000rpm was used. The rotating flywheels had been observed during the spin tests by television monitoring system through the optical port provided on the spin tank cover. The upper surface of the carbon fiber composite rims was colored in white to see the circumferential cracks easily in case it had occurred. A vibration transducer was located near the drive shaft to provide a relative indication of axial vibration during the spin tests.

Rotor with Aluminum Hub

Single rim rotor. The rotor having a composite rim and a aluminum hub had been constructed by a shrinkage fitting with the shrink-fit of 0.4mm. At first, the rotor had been rotated at the peripheral speed of 850m/s and post test visual inspection verified the integrity of the rim and hub. Then, the burst test of the rotor had been conducted and successful peripheral speed of 982m/s had been obtained. This corresponds to an energy density, based upon total rotor weight, of approximately 71Wh/kg.

Multi rim rotor. Since the weight of the aluminum hub is almost the same as that of one rim, the energy density of the single rim rotor is not high. Our next attempt was to make a model having four rims and two aluminum hubs illustrated in Figure 6. The four rims were separately rotated in 800m/s and confirmed to be good, then, they had been bound together in piles and added hubs by a shrinkage fitting. The spin test of the multi rim rotor to the peripheral speed of 800m/s had been succeeded perfectly and there had been no problems in vibration. The stored energy of the rotor at the rotational speed of 800m/s is 548Wh and the energy density is 55Wh/kg.

Rotor with Composite Hub

Single rim rotor. The rotor was assembled with an interference fitting between rim and hub. The rotor was spun to the peripheral speed of 820m/s and stopped by rotor's instability. The rotational speed corresponds to an energy density of 66Wh/kg.

Multi-rim rotor. This rotor was assembled as the same way as that with aluminum hubs. The rotor that is 8.17kg in weight including the four rims is considerably lighter than the rotor with aluminum hub, but the spin test was terminated at peripheral speed of 705m/s by rotors instability.

CONCLUSION

The test results of this study are summarized in Table 1. The maximum rotational speed of 982m/s was obtained by a single-rim rotor with a aluminum hub and maximum stored energy was reached by a multi rim rotor with aluminum hubs. Although the spin test of the multi rim rotor was stopped at the rotational speed of 800m/s, it is properly expected to rotate to the same maximum rotational speed as that of a single rim rotor. In this case, the energy density based upon total weight will become 83Wh/kg. In regard to the rotors with composite hubs, the composite hubs showed a considerable effect in total weight reduction. Additional efforts on rotor dynamics would be expended to show their full performance.

REFERENCES

- (1) Proc. of 1980 Flywheel Technology Symposium, Oct., 1980.
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Table 1 Test results

	Aluminum hub		composite hub	
	single rim	multi rim	single rim	multi rim
Maximum test speed (rpm)	49,330	40,240	41,200	35,450
Maximum peripheral speed (m/s)	982	801	820	705
Stored energy (Wh)	233	548	140	393
Dimensions of rim (ID/OD, t mm)	300/380,25	300/380,100	300/380,25	300/380,100
Weight (kg)				
rim	1.61	6.44	1.61	6.44
hub	1.67	3.54	0.52	1.73
total	3.28	9.98	2.13	8.17
Energy density (Wh/kg)	71.0	54.9	65.7	48.1
Remarks	burst		vibration	vibration

Figure 1 Notation of a rim.

Figure 2 Stress distributions in rotating disks.

Figure 3 Flywheel performance curves of carbon fiber epoxy composite rims.

Figure 4 Single rim rotor with a aluminum hub.

Figure 5 Schema of the aluminum hub.

Figure 6 Multi rim rotor with aluminum hubs.

Figure 7 Single rim rotor with a composite hub.

Figure 8 Multi rim rotor with composite hubs.